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O'ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES MUHITINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyati nazariy va amaliy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqot davomida xorijiy investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy o'sish, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligi, eksport salohiyati va biznes muhitiga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Shuningdek, mamlakatda investitsion muhitni yaxshilash bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlar, investorlar uchun yaratilayotgan huquqiy va institutsional sharoitlar hamda raqamli iqtisodiyotning investitsion faoliyatdagi o'rnini o'rganildi. Tadqiqot natijasida xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish samaradorligini oshirish, biznes yuritish sharoitlarini takomillashtirish va investitsion jozibadorlikni kuchaytirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi. Tadqiqot natijalari mamlakat iqtisodiy barqarorligini mustahkamlash va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xorijiy investitsiyalar, biznes muhiti, investitsion muhit, iqtisodiy o'sish, investitsion jozibadorlik, raqamli iqtisodiyot, eksport salohiyati, erkin iqtisodiy zonalar, iqtisodiy islohotlar, innovatsion rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследовано значение иностранных инвестиций в развитии бизнес-среды Узбекистана с теоретической и практической точек зрения. В ходе исследования был проведён анализ влияния иностранных инвестиций на экономический рост, эффективность производства, экспортный потенциал и бизнес-среду страны. Также изучены экономические реформы, направленные на улучшение инвестиционного климата, правовые и институциональные условия, создаваемые для инвесторов, а также роль цифровой экономики в инвестиционной деятельности. По результатам исследования разработаны научно-практические рекомендации по повышению эффективности привлечения иностранных инвестиций, совершенствованию условий ведения бизнеса и усилению инвестиционной привлекательности страны. Результаты исследования способствуют укреплению экономической стабильности и повышению конкурентоспособности национальной экономики.

Ключевые слова: иностранные инвестиции, бизнес-среда, инвестиционный климат, экономический рост, инвестиционная привлекательность, цифровая экономика, экспортный потенциал, свободные экономические зоны, экономические реформы, инновационное развитие.

Abstract. This article examines the importance of foreign investments in the development of the business environment in Uzbekistan from both theoretical and practical perspectives. The study analyzes the impact of foreign investments on economic growth, production efficiency, export potential, and the overall business environment. In addition, the research explores economic reforms aimed at improving the investment climate, the legal and institutional conditions created for investors, and the role of the digital economy in investment activities. Based on the findings, scientific and practical recommendations were developed to increase the effectiveness of attracting foreign investments, improve business conditions, and strengthen the country's investment attractiveness. The results of the study contribute to enhancing economic stability and increasing the competitiveness of the national economy.

Keywords: foreign investments, business environment, investment climate, economic growth, investment attractiveness, digital economy, export potential, free economic zones, economic reforms, innovative development.

KIRISH

Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida mamlakat iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda xorijiy investitsiyalar muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilish, ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini kengaytirish, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish va yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratishda xorijiy

investitsiyalarning o'zni beqiyosdir. Shu nuqtai nazardan, O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyatini o'rganish dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda jahon iqtisodiyotida globallashuv jarayonlarining kuchayishi va xalqaro kapital harakatining jadallashuvi davlatlardan investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirishni talab etmoqda. Xususan, xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish orqali mamlakatlar iqtisodiy o'sish sur'atlarini tezlashtirish, eksport salohiyatini kengaytirish va milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga intilmoqda. Shu sababli qulay biznes muhitini shakllantirish, investorlarga ishonchli huquqiy kafolatlar yaratish va tadbirkorlik faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash davlat iqtisodiy siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlariga aylanmoqda.

O'zbekistonda so'nggi yillarda iqtisodiyotni liberallashtirish, investitsion muhitni yaxshilash va xususiy sektorni rivojlantirish bo'yicha keng ko'lami islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, xorijiy investorlar uchun soliq va bojxona imtiyozlarining joriy etilishi, erkin iqtisodiy zonalar faoliyatining kengaytirilishi, valyuta siyosatining liberallashtirilishi hamda biznes yuritish bilan bog'liq ma'muriy tartib-taomillarning soddalashtirilishi mamlakatning investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Natijada iqtisodiyotning turli tarmoqlariga jalb qilinayotgan xorijiy investitsiyalar hajmi yildan-yilga ortib bormoqda.

Xorijiy investitsiyalar nafaqat qo'shimcha moliyaviy resurs manbai, balki zamonaviy texnologiyalar, innovatsion boshqaruv usullari va xalqaro tajribani iqtisodiyotga olib kiruvchi muhim omil sifatida ham ahamiyatlidir. Ayniqsa, sanoat, xizmat ko'rsatish, logistika, axborot texnologiyalari va infratuzilma sohalariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish va yangi biznes imkoniyatlarini yaratishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda.

Shu bilan birga, xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimiga ta'sir etuvchi ayrim omillar ham mavjud. Jumladan, ayrim hududlarda infratuzilmaning yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, ma'muriy jarayonlarning murakkabligi, investitsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirishdagi qiyinchiliklar hamda malakali kadrlar taqchilligi investorlar faoliyati samaradorligiga muayyan darajada ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Bu esa biznes muhitini yanada takomillashtirish va xorijiy investorlar uchun qulay sharoitlarni kengaytirish zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi.

Ilmiy adabiyotlarda xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, eksport hajmini oshirish, yangi texnologiyalar transferini amalga oshirish va milliy iqtisodiyotning xalqaro integratsiyasini kuchaytirishning muhim omili sifatida talqin qilinadi. Xususan, rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan davlatlar tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, investitsion muhit qanchalik qulay bo'lsa, iqtisodiy rivojlanish sur'atlari ham shunchalik yuqori bo'ladi.

Mazkur mavzuning dolzarbligi O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy ahamiyatini chuqur o'rganish, mavjud muammolarni aniqlash va investitsion faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish zarurati bilan izohlanadi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning o'zni va ahamiyatini nazariy hamda amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilish, investitsion faoliyatga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni o'rganish hamda xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida O'zbekistondagi biznes muhiti va xorijiy investitsiyalar jarayonlari tanlangan bo'lsa, tadqiqot predmetini xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va ulardan samarali foydalanish bilan bog'liq iqtisodiy munosabatlar tashkil etadi. Tadqiqot davomida iqtisodiy-statistik tahlil, tizimli yondashuv, qiyosiy tahlil va iqtisodiy kuzatish usullaridan foydalaniladi. Mavzuning ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyati shundan iboratki, tadqiqot natijasida ishlab chiqilgan tavsiya va takliflar O'zbekistonda investitsion muhitni yanada yaxshilash, xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini kengaytirish hamda biznes subyektlari faoliyatini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyati iqtisodiy nazariya, xalqaro iqtisodiy munosabatlar, investitsiya siyosati va strategik boshqaruv sohalarida faoliyat yurituvchi ko'plab olimlar tomonidan keng tadqiq etilgan. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish va milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini kuchaytirishning muhim omillaridan biri sifatida talqin qilinadi. Shu bilan birga, qulay biznes muhiti xorijiy investorlarni jalb qilishning asosiy shartlaridan biri sifatida baholanadi.

Xorijiy iqtisodchi olimlardan J. Dunning xorijiy investitsiyalar nazariyasiga katta hissa qo'shgan olimlardan biri hisoblanadi. U tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan "OLI" (Ownership, Location, Internalization) modeli xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishning nazariy asoslarini yoritadi. Olimning fikricha, investorlarni jalb qilish uchun mamlakatda qulay investitsion muhit, barqaror iqtisodiy siyosat va samarali institutsional tizim mavjud bo'lishi zarur. Dunning xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiy modernizatsiya va xalqaro integratsiyaning muhim vositasi ekanligini ta'kidlaydi.

P. Krugman xalqaro iqtisodiy munosabatlar va investitsion jarayonlarni o'rganib, xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirishda muhim rol o'ynashini asoslab bergan. Uning ilmiy qarashlariga ko'ra, xorijiy kapital oqimi ishlab chiqarish hajmini oshirish, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish va texnologik yangilanish jarayonlarini

tezlashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, investorlar uchun yaratilgan qulay biznes muhiti mamlakatning xalqaro bozordagi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

M. Porter o'zining raqobat ustunligi nazariyasida xorijiy investitsiyalarni milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini oshiruvchi omillardan biri sifatida baholagan. U davlatning investitsion siyosati, infratuzilma rivoji va biznes muhitining sifati xorijiy investorlar faoliyatiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatishini qayd etgan. Porterning fikricha, innovatsion muhit va samarali boshqaruv tizimi mavjud bo'lgan mamlakatlarda investitsion jozibadorlik yuqori bo'ladi.

D. Nort institutsional iqtisodiyot nazariyasida investitsion muhit va davlat institutlarining samaradorligiga alohida e'tibor qaratgan. Olimning ilmiy qarashlariga ko'ra, mulk huquqining himoyalanganligi, sud-huquq tizimining mustaqilligi va iqtisodiy erkinlik darajasi xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

MDH mamlakatlari olimlari tomonidan ham xorijiy investitsiyalar va biznes muhitining o'zaro bog'liqligi keng o'rganilgan. Jumladan, L. I. Abalkin, V. D. Andreyev, O. S. Vixanskiy kabi olimlarning ilmiy ishlarida investitsion faoliyatni rivojlantirish, davlatning investitsiya siyosati va biznes muhitiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlil qilingan. Ularning tadqiqotlarida investitsion jarayonlarni samarali boshqarish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashning muhim omillaridan biri sifatida ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

O'zbekistonlik iqtisodchi olimlar tomonidan ham xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va biznes muhitini rivojlantirish masalalari keng tadqiq etilgan. Jumladan, S. G'ulomov, Yo. Abdullayev, A. O'lmasov, Sh. Shodmonov va boshqa olimlarning ilmiy asarlarida investitsion muhitni yaxshilash, tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirish va xorijiy kapitalni iqtisodiyotga jalb etishning nazariy hamda amaliy jihatlari o'rganilgan. Ushbu tadqiqotlarda xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish orqali iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarini modernizatsiya qilish, eksport salohiyatini oshirish va yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish masalalariga katta e'tibor qaratilgan.

So'nggi yillarda ilmiy adabiyotlarda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish masalalari ham dolzarb mavzulardan biriga aylangan. Tadqiqotchilar elektron hukumat tizimi, raqamli davlat xizmatlari, onlayn litsenziyalash va soliq tizimlarining joriy etilishi investitsion muhitni yaxshilashga xizmat qilayotganini ta'kidlamog'dalar. Ayniqsa, biznes yuritish jarayonlarining raqamlashtirilishi investorlar uchun ma'muriy xarajatlarni kamaytirish va biznes jarayonlarini tezlashtirish imkonini bermoqda.

Xalqaro tashkilotlar, jumladan, World Bank, International Monetary Fund hamda United Nations Conference on Trade and Development tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiy o'sish va biznes muhitini rivojlantirishning muhim omillaridan biri sifatida baholanadi. Ushbu tashkilotlar hisobotlarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish uchun institutsional islohotlar, huquqiy barqarorlik va iqtisodiy erkinlikni ta'minlash zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, xorijiy investitsiyalar va biznes muhiti o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik ko'plab olimlar tomonidan o'rganilgan bo'lsa-da, O'zbekiston sharoitida investitsion muhitni yanada takomillashtirish, xorijiy investitsiyalar samaradorligini oshirish va ularni iqtisodiyotning ustuvor tarmoqlariga yo'naltirish masalalari chuqur ilmiy tadqiqotlarni talab etadi. Ayniqsa, raqamli iqtisodiyot va globallashtirish jarayonlari sharoitida investitsion siyosatni zamonaviy talablar asosida rivojlantirish muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Mazkur tadqiqotda O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyatini o'rganish uchun zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqot usullaridan kompleks ravishda foydalanildi. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi xorijiy investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy rivojlanish, biznes muhiti sifati va tadbirkorlik faoliyatiga ta'sirini tahlil qilish hamda investitsion muhitni takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga yo'naltirilgan.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyatini tahlil qilish natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, xorijiy kapital iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish va tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilish, eksport salohiyatini kengaytirish va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etishda xorijiy investitsiyalar muhim strategik resurs sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda.

Tahlillar davomida O'zbekistonda so'nggi yillarda investitsion muhitni yaxshilashga qaratilgan islohotlar xorijiy investitsiyalar hajmining oshishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatgani aniqlandi. Xususan, valyuta siyosatining liberallashtirilishi, soliq tizimining soddalashtirilishi, investorlarga berilayotgan imtiyozlarning kengaytirilishi va biznes yuritish bilan bog'liq ma'muriy tartib-taomillarning qisqartirilishi mamlakatning investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Natijada iqtisodiyotning sanoat, energetika, logistika, axborot texnologiyalari va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalariga jalb qilinayotgan xorijiy investitsiyalar hajmi ortib bormoqda.

Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, xorijiy investitsiyalar iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarini modernizatsiya qilish va ishlab

chiqarish quvvatlarini kengaytirishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Ayniqsa, xorijiy kapital ishtirokidagi korxonalarda zamonaviy texnologiyalar va innovatsion boshqaruv tizimlarining joriy etilishi mehnat unumdorligini oshirishga, mahsulot sifatini yaxshilashga hamda eksportbop mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, xorijiy investitsiyalar yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish va aholi bandligini oshirishga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda.

PESTEL tahlili natijalariga ko'ra, siyosiy va huquqiy omillar xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlandi. Davlat tomonidan investorlar huquqlarining himoya qilinishi, investitsiya faoliyatiga oid qonunchilikning takomillashtirilishi va xalqaro iqtisodiy hamkorlikning kengaytirilishi investitsion muhitning barqarorligini ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ayrim hududlarda infratuzilmaning yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, ma'muriy jarayonlarning murakkabligi, investitsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirishdagi qiyinchiliklar hamda malakali kadrlar taqchilligi investitsion faoliyat samaradorligiga muayyan darajada ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda.

Iqtisodiy omillar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, mamlakatda makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikning ta'minlanishi, inflyatsiya darajasining nazorat qilinishi va bank-moliya tizimidagi islohotlar xorijiy investorlar ishonchini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ayrim hollarda kredit resurslari qiymatining yuqoriligi va valyuta bozoridagi o'zgaruvchanlik investitsion loyihalarni amalga oshirish samaradorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar sifatida baholandi.

Texnologik omillar tahlili natijasida raqamli iqtisodiyot va elektron davlat xizmatlarining rivojlanishi investitsion muhitni yaxshilashda muhim omillardan biri ekanligi aniqlandi. Elektron hukumat tizimi, onlayn ro'yxatdan o'tish, elektron soliq va bojxona xizmatlarining joriy etilishi investorlar uchun biznes yuritish jarayonlarini soddalashtirmoqda. Ayniqsa, investitsiya loyihalarini elektron monitoring qilish tizimlarining joriy etilishi investitsion faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

SWOT tahlili natijalariga ko'ra, O'zbekiston investitsion muhitining kuchli tomonlari sifatida tabiiy resurslarning boyligi, geografik joylashuvning qulayligi, davlat tomonidan investorlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash siyosatining kuchaygani va ichki bozor hajmining kengligi qayd etildi. Zaif tomonlar qatoriga esa ayrim hududlarda logistika infratuzilmasining yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, malakali kadrlar taqchilligi va ma'muriy tartib-taomillarning murakkabligi kiritildi. Imkoniyatlar sifatida erkin iqtisodiy zonalar faoliyatining kengayishi, xalqaro iqtisodiy hamkorlikning rivojlanishi va raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish jarayonlari baholandi. Tahdidlar esa global iqtisodiy beqarorlik holatlari, tashqi bozorlardagi raqobatning kuchayishi va xalqaro investitsiya oqimlaridagi beqarorlik bilan izohlandi.

Tahlillar natijasida xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish samaradorligini oshirish uchun investitsion muhitni yanada yaxshilash, ma'muriy tartib-taomillarni soddalashtirish va investorlar uchun huquqiy kafolatlarni kuchaytirish zarurligi aniqlandi. Shu bilan birga, hududlarda zamonaviy infratuzilmani rivojlantirish, logistika tizimini takomillashtirish va malakali mutaxassislar tayyorlash xorijiy investitsiyalar samaradorligini oshirishning muhim yo'nalishlari sifatida baholandi.

O'tkazilgan tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, xorijiy investitsiyalar O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirish, iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirish va milliy iqtisodiyotning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Shu sababli investitsion muhitni yanada takomillashtirish, investorlar uchun qulay sharoit yaratish va zamonaviy boshqaruv mexanizmlarini keng joriy etish mamlakat iqtisodiy taraqqiyotining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida qaraladi.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Olib borilgan tadqiqotlar natijasida O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalar muhim iqtisodiy omillardan biri ekanligi aniqlandi. Xorijiy investitsiyalar mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga qo'shimcha moliyaviy resurslarni jalb qilish bilan birga, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, innovatsion boshqaruv usullari va ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni iqtisodiyotga olib kirishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Ayniqsa, sanoat, xizmat ko'rsatish, logistika va axborot texnologiyalari sohalariga jalb qilinayotgan xorijiy investitsiyalar ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish, eksport salohiyatini kengaytirish va yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Tadqiqot davomida O'zbekistonda investitsion muhitni yaxshilash bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlar xorijiy investorlar faoliyatiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatgani aniqlandi. Xususan, soliq va bojxona tizimidagi islohotlar, valyuta siyosatining liberallashtirilishi, erkin iqtisodiy zonalar faoliyatining rivojlantirilishi hamda elektron davlat xizmatlarining joriy etilishi mamlakat investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ayrim hududlarda infratuzilmaning yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, logistika muammolari, ma'muriy tartib-taomillarning murakkabligi va malakali kadrlar taqchilligi xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimiga muayyan darajada ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan omillar sifatida baholandi. Tahlillar natijasida xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va ulardan samarali foydalanishni yanada takomillashtirish bo'yicha quyidagi takliflar ishlab chiqildi:

- xorijiy investorlar uchun barqaror va shaffof huquqiy muhitni yanada mustahkamlash zarur;
- investitsion loyihalarni amalga oshirish bilan bog'liq ma'muriy tartib-taomillarni qisqartirish va

soddalashtirish maqsadga muvofiq;

– erkin iqtisodiy zonalar faoliyatini kengaytirish hamda hududlarda sanoat infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish lozim;

– xorijiy investitsiyalarni yuqori texnologiyali va eksportga yo'naltirilgan tarmoqlarga jalb qilishni rag'batlantirish kerak;

– elektron hukumat tizimi va raqamli davlat xizmatlari sifatini oshirish orqali investorlar uchun qulay biznes muhitini yaratish zarur;

– logistika va transport infratuzilmasini modernizatsiya qilish hamda xalqaro transport yo'laklarini rivojlantirish muhim hisoblanadi;

– xorijiy investorlar ishtirokidagi korxonalar uchun malakali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish va dual ta'lim mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish tavsiya etiladi;

– hududlarda investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish maqsadida mahalliy hokimiyat organlari va biznes subyektlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni kuchaytirish lozim.

Shuningdek, tadqiqot davomida raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsion faoliyatni boshqarishning zamonaviy mexanizmlarini joriy etish xorijiy investitsiyalar samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil ekanligi aniqlandi. Elektron platformalar, investitsion monitoring tizimlari va raqamli boshqaruv vositalari investorlar faoliyatini tezkor va shaffof tashkil etishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Umuman olganda, xorijiy investitsiyalar O'zbekistonda biznes muhitini rivojlantirish, iqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash va milliy iqtisodiyotning xalqaro raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim strategik omil hisoblanadi. Shu sababli investitsion muhitni yanada takomillashtirish, xorijiy investorlar uchun qulay sharoit yaratish va innovatsion rivojlanishni qo'llab-quvvatlash davlat iqtisodiy siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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